

C-SCALE Copernicus Data Lookup, Access and Dissemination Final Implementation Report

Status:	Final	Planned due date:	28 February 2023
Version:	V1.0	Submission date:	28 February 2023
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Related WP:	WP2	Document Ref:	D2.2
Dissemination Level:	Public (PU)		
Document Link:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7682873		

Deliverable Abstract

The C-SCALE Data Federation brings together European providers of Earth observation product archives to facilitate seamless access from analytic workloads running in EOSC, and to prototype a distributed long-term archive of Copernicus data. Essential functionality has been implemented within the C-SCALE Project to enable product discovery and access across the federation. This document discusses the status and details of that implementation.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017529.

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C-SCALE receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101017529.

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DOCUMENT LOG

<i>Issue</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Comment</i>	<i>Author(s)</i>
VO.1	24 January 2023	Initial document structure	Zdeněk Šustr
VO.2	13 February 2023	Document ready for extra-WP review	Zdeněk Šustr
VO.3	22 February 2023	Reviewers' comments implemented	Zdeněk Šustr
V1.0	28 February 2023	Final release	Zdeněk Šustr

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AMB	Activity Management Board
API	Application Programming Interface
C-SCALE	Copernicus – eoSC AnaLytics Engine
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
GOCDDB	Grid Configuration Database
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IDP	Identity Provider
EO-MQS	Earth Observation Metadata Query Service
OIDC	OpenID Connect
SAFE	Standard Archive Format for Europe
STAC	Spatial Temporal Asset Catalog
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VO	Virtual Organisation
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

C-SCALE brings together experts in Copernicus and European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) services and solutions to provide a blueprint for solving the challenge of Copernicus full-term data archive. This is being addressed by federating existing operators of Earth observation data archives to create a distributed archive with the ambition to achieve global coverage.

Partners in the proposed federation maintain various Earth observation archives with limited areas of interest. These include national archives, or archives of certain geographic regions and product types maintained, e.g., for specific research purposes. The C-SCALE project aims at *enabling user workflows* that make using the diverse resources in the federation as simple as working with a single resource site, i.e., compensating for the distributed nature of the archive and making traversing different resources available within the federation as seamless as possible.

This document reports on the implementation, integration and support work carried out to establish the C-SCALE Data Federation.

Main Areas of Integration

C-SCALE has identified two main areas of focus, within which all the integration work could be categorized. They are:

1. **Discoverability of the data**, making sure that data could be discovered across the federation with the same ease and with the same approach as if working with a single provider, regardless of which partner actually holds them.
2. **Accessibility of the data**, making sure that the data could be reached regardless of location (in terms of both geography and network topology) and that the need to register as a user separately for multiple partners in the federation could be completely avoided.

Discoverability

The ability to identify the location of data matching user requirements is achieved by having the participating sites expose a common, standards-based query interface, and providing a search aggregation service (the EO Metadata Query Service – EO-MQS). EO-MQS arches over all the discovery interfaces in the federation and acts as a single point of contact to users. Their queries are redistributed among relevant provider sites, and the resulting responses are then collated and returned back to the user.

Accessibility

Earth observation products offered by members in the federation are typically open, available for use free of charge. Yet it may still be necessary for various reasons to identify or at least classify the user on access. Therefore the data providers integrate with an identity federation implemented by the EGI Check-in Service [R1]. This is not primarily motivated by the need to make authorization decisions since the download of Earth observation products available from the federation is mostly unrestricted,

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but more by the need to keep track of which communities, professions and scientific domains use the information to what extent.

Outcomes

Components and services resulting from the effort to federate Copernicus data resources within C-SCALE form the basis of two EOSC services:

- FedEarthData [R2]
- EO Metadata Query Service [R3]

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1 Introduction

This document details the implementation of the C-SCALE Data Federation. The proposed architecture was introduced in the previous deliverable *D2.1 C-SCALE Copernicus Data Access and Querying Design* [R4] and the individual components outlined therein have been developed over the course of the C-SCALE project. The following text reiterates on the originally planned principles (Section 2) and explains how they have been adjusted and expanded through the process of user co-design. It then goes on to explain the status of the required components, and their integration into the wider ecosystem of other C-SCALE resources and of EOSC in general (Sections 3 and 4). Finally it discusses the status and results of the work in general (Section 5).

One of the frequently invoked principles for EOSC datasets, as well as a major objective for C-SCALE, is the principle of FAIR data. A FAIR-principles questionnaire for C-SCALE data is attached as an Appendix to this report.

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2 Data Federation Principles

The C-SCALE Data Federation is designed to be light-weight, rely on existing services and tools wherever available, and make joining it as easy as possible. Specifically for its light-weight aspect it strives to avoid duplication of data, fully discloses its distributed nature, and promotes the idea that the same level of service should be provided to users accessing a partner site through federation interfaces as well as through a partner's own, in many cases pre-existing ones. A strong emphasis is also being put on supporting automated workflows, i.e., making sure that finding data across the federation and obtaining them for processing can be done without human interaction.

To join the federation, a prospective partner is expected to make their data discoverable and accessible. Specifically for *discoverability* this means integrating with the EO Metadata Query Service, which provides an outward-facing STAC API and STAC Browser to allow users to look up data available from any of the partners in the federation. The selection of STAC [R5] as the common discovery protocol for C-SCALE has resulted from comparing multiple options during the design phase of C-SCALE and discussed in the previous deliverable D2.1.

For *accessibility*, all partners are required to enable HTTP(S) access to their data. Access can be completely open, but the obligation for users to authenticate on access may also be imposed by partners who require that users provide specific attributes when accessing the data. If that is the case, providers integrate with the EGI Check-in service.

2.1 Data Federation providers' Catalogue

Not to be confused with the distributed catalogue of Earth observation data available in the federation, discussed in Section 3, the providers' catalogue is a simple registry of partners and endpoints to be considered when looking up data across the federation. It is not implemented as a separate component but relies on the Grid Configuration Database (GOCDDB) [R6], where a new scope tag C-SCALE has been registered to distinguish member sites of the C-SCALE Data Federation. Members use tools already existing in GOCDDB to register their protocol endpoints, where STAC endpoints are required but the registration of endpoints implementing other relevant discovery protocols is also encouraged.

As in all other cases, the use by automated workflows is supported and the registration is not only human-, but more importantly also machine-readable. For example, the following URLs can be used to identify resource providers in the Data Federation:

- Sites with the C-SCALE scope tag: https://goc.egi.eu/gocdbpi/public/?method=get_site_list&scope=C-SCALE
- Service endpoints grouped by site: https://goc.egi.eu/gocdbpi/public/?method=get_service_endpoint&scope=C-SCALE

The latter is used by the EO-MQS to identify sites providing STAC endpoints. Currently C-SCALE services are registered in GOCDDB under a *custom service* type, which allowed for easy format adjustment during the project. Now settled, a purpose-specific service type can be defined in GOCDDB as a next step since the data format is now clearly established.

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3 Data Lookup Implementation

The implementation of components to enable discovery of Earth observation products had to involve all partners in the Data Federation work package. Firstly there was the EO Metadata Query Service – a central component to broker STAC queries, and secondly there was harmonization of metadata catalogues by individual participating sites.

By design of the federation and the EO Metadata Query Service, there are multiple options for partners to integrate with the central discovery service (Fig 3.1 – page 11):

1. Provide a standalone *mapper* component (microservice), which would translate between STAC and the site’s selected interface protocol, such as CSW or OpenSearch.
2. Contribute back-end code to the EO Metadata Query Service, performing the translation between STAC and the site’s supported protocol.
3. Provide a native STAC API at their own site.

For different reasons outlined below, all current partners in the C-SCALE Data federation have selected the final option – providing a bespoke STAC API at their sites, in certain cases with a mapper component on the background. Still, the other approaches remain open to future joiners of the federation.

A detailed report on implementing the individual components required to establish the federation is given in the following sections.

3.1 The EO Metadata Query Service

The C-SCALE EO Metadata Query Service (EO-MQS) implements a STAC-compliant API, responsible for distributing incoming queries across federated sites and delivering a consolidated response comprising the aggregation of results. The EO-MQS offers a unified endpoint for accessing all STAC collections within the federation and features a search interface that accommodates the core parameters specified in the STAC API Item Search specification. Additional attributes that go beyond the core specification can also be used as long as any partner supports them in their catalogue, but the current implementation of the EO-MQS is not capable of indicating which STAC extension is supported by which partner.

Implementation

The central building block for the development of the EO-MQS is *stac-fastapi* [R7], an open-source Python library for implementing FastAPI [R8] applications complying with the STAC API specifications. More precisely, the Postgres backend implementation with *SQLAlchemy* [R9] served as the starting point for the development of the EO-MQS application. While existing implementations were designed to work with a backend solution like a PostgreSQL database to read data from or write records to, the requirements for the EO-MQS were different: The EO-MQS would only serve as a broker to handle

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Figure 3.1: Original proposal for the EO Metadata Query Service design

incoming requests and outgoing responses. No data would actually be needed to be stored. Instead, STAC data stemming from various sources needed to be aggregated and consolidated into a single response.

To realise this functionality, a custom client module was developed and incorporated into the existing code base. The client implements functions to handle incoming HTTP requests following the STAC API-defined structure of API endpoints:

- /collections
- /collections/{collectionId}
- /collections/{collectionId}/items
- /collections/{collectionId}/items/{featureId}
- /search

Essentially, the client accepts incoming FastAPI Request objects and modifies their request body and URL according to the list of available data provider URLs. This list is auto-generated using information stored in the GOCDB. More details on this below in the section about the GOCDB client management.

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Browsing

The design of the EO-MQS client functionality takes into account the differences in STAC response types returned by each collection endpoint, as well as the possibility of duplicate Collection IDs from multiple data providers. For instance, `/collections` returns a list of Collection objects, while `/collections/{collectionId}` returns a single Collection JSON. Generating the list of objects is achieved by looping over the available data providers and concatenating the responses to a single list. For the sake of uniqueness, the EO-MQS prepends the provider ID to the collection ID.

Example: a collection with the ID `sentinel-2-11c` exists in multiple locations, at provider EODC and at provider CollGS_CZ. The list of collections returned by the EO-MQS will appear as follows:

- `EODC|sentinel-2-11c`
- `CollGS_CZ|sentinel-2-11c`

This is additional information that might be included in the EO-MQS user's workflow to more precisely define STAC queries. However, specifying the provider ID is not mandatory for the API search, nor is it required for the collection endpoint that returns a single JSON response. In the absence of provider ID specification, the EO-MQS will retrieve the first collection with a matching collection ID by sequentially processing the data providers in the same order they are registered in the GOCDB, i.e., based on the site ID.

Example: `/collections/sentinel-2-11c` returns `EODC|sentinel-2-11c`, while a specific query for `/collections/CollGS_CZ|sentinel-2-11c` will return the collection hosted at the specified site.

The example query results into EODC collection being offered first, because EODC's site ID in GOCDB is 2 285, while CollGS_CZ's site ID is 3 032. The same principle applies to the `/items` endpoints as well, since they are linked to a specific collection ID. This default behaviour is motivated by simplicity. In the current implementation of EO-MQS, the client queries the GOCDB and simply uses the results as they are returned by the server. A more sophisticated approach, such as a selection based on performance, reputation, or other metrics, or a more naïve one, such as round robin or random selection, can be considered for implementation in future releases.

To make the process of browsing the catalog even more comprehensive and user-friendly where required, EO-MQS also utilizes the STAC Browser tool [R10] to visually present the federated data catalogue, providing the users with another easy way to discover relevant data.

Searching

The browsing feature for the `/collections` endpoint operates by following links within JSON responses and can be implemented using a static file-based STAC catalogue. However, a dynamic catalogue search involves communication between interfaces through HTTP requests. Realising the federated `/search` endpoint is therefore more complex.

While the current implementation of the `/search` endpoint is highly suitable for robotic use, it may become somewhat awkward for interactive use by humans. This will be addressed by the

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upcoming major version of the STAC Browser (v. 3) that will also support searching. The expected version is currently not available in a stable release, but a preview version for EO-MQS is already accessible for evaluation [R11].

Pagination

One of the challenges in this context lies in the fact that APIs are typically designed to utilise pagination techniques, i.e., to only return a subset of results, which is also directly impacted by the implemented sorting method. Therefore, the retrieval of all records from every data source poses a challenge, particularly when the total list of results is comparably long, due to the time and memory requirements involved. The challenge of retrieving all records was already addressed in deliverable *D2.1 C-SCALE Copernicus Data Access and Querying Design* during the project's conceptual phase, and two options for dealing with it were identified:

- most complete pagination,
- most responsive pagination.

The most complete pagination approach offers global sorting of results from various data providers to deliver the optimal response to the EO-MQS user. This option is achieved through a recursive search function in the client, where all results are gathered and sorted prior to presenting a paginated response to the end user. However, due to performance considerations, this option is not the default choice.

The most responsive option performs pagination by consistently returning a fixed number of records per data provider and page, with the fixed number potentially varying between data providers based on the default or maximum page size at each provider. The EO-MQS implements an option allowing the user to set the page limit through an additional query parameter, with a default value of 10.

Serializing

The core module of the base package was modified to translate and serialize HTTP responses into STAC items. The serializer ensures the validity of external and dynamically created internal links, for example, by adding the relevant provider IDs to the collection links or include tokens in the pagination links.

Sorting

Sorting is performed using the `datetime` property, but the user may choose an alternative sorting method. It is possible, however, that different implementations might have varying depth and detail of their respective metadata descriptions, which could lead to unexpected results when using sorting parameters that are not part of the STAC core specification, i.e., of the minimum set of required attributes. The `datetime` property is the only required property in this sense that is useful for sorting. The full list of properties required by the STAC Core specification, and therefore supported by EO-MQS, is as follows:

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- `limit`
- `bbox`
- `datetime`
- `intersects`
- `ids`
- `collections`

To overcome this limitation, it is advisable to establish a common vocabulary for attribute names. This will ensure that parameters used for sorting are consistent and lead to the desired results for the end user. The C-SCALE project has laid down early groundwork to establish a common vocabulary, but this understanding is limited to the members of the federation and cannot be generalized to the greater STAC community. Regardless, future work will focus on implementing a more extensive list of features, with the harmonization of attribute names being a key prerequisite for searching based on specific metadata attributes. For example, to filter satellite imagery by cloud coverage, the attribute must have a consistent name across the federation, otherwise using multiple names such as `cloud_coverage`, `coverage`, `cloud_coverage_percentage`, etc. will negatively impact the user experience.

GOCDDB client management

The GOCDDB is an EGI service that catalogues participating sites and services in the EGI Federation, including specific endpoints (see Section 2.1). To access the information stored in GOCDDB, an API has been provided that returns the data in XML format. To retrieve and process this information, a GOCDDB client has been developed as part of the EO-MQS package. The client identifies data providers that are relevant for the EO-MQS by searching for endpoints within the `c-scale` scope and having an endpoint registered under the name STAC. This process is dynamic and new data providers can be added to the EO-MQS without much effort, just by registering a new endpoint in GOCDDB within the specified scope and name. The list is refreshed hourly. As a result, the EO-MQS stays up-to-date with the latest data providers and their respective endpoints, allowing it to provide access to the most comprehensive set of data available.

Documentation

EO-MQS includes a comprehensive help page [R12] that provides information on how to use the system, including examples for programming languages such as Python or Bash.

3.2 Terrascope STAC API

The Terrascope STAC API was developed in the context of the C-SCALE project. It is implemented as an adapter built on top of the already existing Terrascope OpenSearch – OSCARS (OpenSearch CAtalogue for Remote Sensing). It converts STAC requests into OpenSearch requests. The OpenSearch

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Figure 3.2: Terrascope STAC search – block diagram

responses are converted into STAC responses. The Terrascope OpenSearch service is implemented using Spring Bot [R13] and stores collection and product metadata in an Elasticsearch [R14] backend.

The adapter uses the *stac-fastapi* library. The implementation uses a custom client class that implements the STAC API endpoints and depends on the TerraCatalogue OpenSearch API endpoints as its data source.

The code is available in a public Github repository [R15] and the API documentation is available online [R16].

The service implements the STAC API version v1.0.0-rc.1. The current Terrascope STAC implementation does not support STAC extensions.

Compared to the Terrascope OpenSearch service, STAC only offers a subset of the functionality:

- no filtering when searching for collection(s);
- fewer filtering parameters when searching for product(s) (e.g., no support for `resolution`, `tileId`, `cloudCover`, `accessedFrom`, ...);
- no support for different asset modes (local storage, HTTP, S3)

3.3 DHuS-based Sites STAC API

DHuS [R17] is an open source tool made available by ESA to members of the Sentinels Collaborative Ground Segment, and implemented by SERCO and GAEL Systems. It is used by Copernicus hubs (Open

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Access Hub/SciHub [R18], API Hub, collaborative hubs, DataHub relays, etc.) and also by a subset of national collaborative ground segment mirrors to redistribute Sentinel imagery. Within the C-SCALE Data federation this product is being used by CESNET and GRNET.

DHuS implements two distinct discovery protocols: OpenSearch [R19] and OData [R20]. Among the two, OData is not suitable for generic spatio-temporal data discovery since it does not support positional attributes. It is still used in the background, though, for actual access to data. OpenSearch is more powerful in terms of precisising a query for data, and indeed the original plan for C-SCALE integration expected to implement a translator component between STAC and OpenSearch to enable Earth observation data discovery at DHuS-based sites. This would have been an approach similar to what VITO deployed for Terrascope as described in Section 3.2. In the end, it turned out that OpenSearch as implemented in DHuS did not support sufficient detail of metadata, not so much in terms of query attributes, but more importantly in terms of response granularity. For example, STAC represents every Sentinel product as an *item* including multiple *assets*, i.e., individual wavelength band image files. On the other hand, OpenSearch, as implemented by DHuS, does not provide that level of detail in describing individual products. What is more, that information is not even available in a structured form in its database, but must be reconstructed from multiple metadata files (manifests) packaged with each product.

Therefore DHuS-based sites chose to deploy stand-alone STAC Catalogues and populate them with data reconstructed from actual Earth observation data in their storage. As a result, each site exposes a STAC API, which can be contacted by the EO Metadata Query Service.

The actual catalogue service makes use of Resto [R21], a STAC-enabled open source metadata catalogue.

To populate the catalogue, the following steps are performed for each product that should be advertised through the STAC catalogue, and, subsequently, the EO Metadata Query Service:

1. Product type (including Sentinel platform and processing level) are determined and relevant metadata files, which are required for metadata reconstruction, are extracted from the stored archive. The target collection is determined at the same time.
2. Tools from the STAC Tools Suite [R22] are used to produce a STAC-compliant description of the product (item).
3. Asset URLs are modified so that individual image files can actually be retrieved through the OData interface for DHuS (as demonstrated in Table 3.1).
4. The resulting STAC item structure is uploaded into the catalogue.

Local Path	S2B_MSIL1C_20230204T100119_N0509_R122_T33UVR_20230204T104152.SAFE/GRANULE/L1C_T33UVR_A030893_20230204T100117/IMG_DATA/T33UVR_20230204T100119_B08.jp2
Path in DHuS	https://dhr1.cesnet.cz/odata/v1/Products(%271a1ec6f8-01d8-424c-a147-6310b7b9acb9%27)/Nodes(%27S2B_MSIL1C_20230204T100119_N0509_R122_T33UVR_20230204T104152.SAFE%27)/Nodes(%27GRANULE%27)/Nodes(%27L1C_T33UVR_A030893_20230204T100117%27)/Nodes(%27IMG_DATA%27)/Nodes(%27T33UVR_20230204T100119_B08.jp2%27)/%24value

Table 3.1: Example difference between local path to a Sentinel asset (in this case a near infra-red band at 833.0 nm), and path to access it over the OData protocol in DHuS.

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This process is automated to keep the catalogue filled with metadata for fresh products as they get produced.

The first generation of scripts that perform these tasks are publicly available as part of the DHuS Tools repository [R23] maintained by CESNET:

- `register-stac.sh` to generate and register STAC metadata, implementing the four steps outlined above
- `gist/check-new-register-stac.sh` to identify products freshly ingested into DHuS datatypes.

Actual STAC-API endpoints for partners relying on DHuS are available at CESNET [R24] and GRNET [R25].

3.4 EODC STAC API

By its original, pre-C-SCALE design, EODC exposes metadata through a CSW (Catalogue Service for the Web) interface. Similar to other partners in the Data federation, the original intention was to establish a mapping between the CSW and STAC metadata standards. This turned out to be unfeasible, wherefore it was decided to establish a stand-alone STAC service, while maintaining the existing CSW interface in parallel. This approach ensures that metadata remain accessible through the CSW interface while simultaneously providing a novel and efficient solution for STAC metadata exposure, which is required for the EO-MQS.

The EODC STAC API, currently version 1.0.0, is implemented using the *stac-fastapi* library – a Python-based framework for building high-performance STAC APIs. The API uses a *pgstac* backend, which is essentially a PostgreSQL database optimized for storing STAC data.

For STAC metadata generation, EODC follows an approach similar to that described for CESNET in Section 3.3. STAC collections and, more importantly, individual items are processed by tools from the *stactools* package. On top of that, EODC offers its own product type *Sentinel-1 Sigma0*, which gets annotated with metadata generated by an in-house tool similar to those from the *stactools* suite. Employing similar tools to generate metadata brings about the added benefit that even attributes that are not formally standardized across the C-SCALE federation, they are practically the same for all partners sharing a common technical base.

The STAC catalogue is kept up-to-date through integration with the data stream workflow management. STAC item creation and ingestion into the catalogue is included in the process, allowing for automatic updates. Additionally, BASH scripts have been created to add historic data to the catalogue upon request. This combination of automatic updates and manual operations ensures the catalogue remains current and comprehensive.

STAC Extensions

The EODC STAC API implements several STAC extensions, including SAR, SAT, EO, PROJECTION, and ALTERNATE_ASSETS, to enhance the functionality of the API. These extensions, albeit only partly stable in terms of maturity, provide additional information on the items accessible through the API, such

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as satellite data or observational metadata. These additional metadata make it possible for users to identify specific data matching their requirements more easily.

One of the features enabled by the implementation of the ALTERNATE_ASSETS extension is the ability to provide multiple access locations for individual assets. Indeed, there are up to three different locations for each STAC asset:

- URL pointing to Web server – the main mode of access for users accessing the data through the C-SCALE federation,
- full local path on the file system at EODC, which is convenient for local users, although it does not have global applicability,
- URL, if applicable, pointing to the location of the asset on the ESA Open Access Hub (SciHub), where the same asset may be available for download for the general public.

This offers multiple options for accessing the assets and facilitates use of the data in various applications. It also shows how support for a local user base can be maintained while opening the resource to a wider community at the same time.

3.5 CreoDIAS STAC API

The CreoDIAS STAC API [R26] was implemented as a web service interface to query over a group of STAC items held in a database. All fields included in CreoDIAS STAC API are consistent with the STAC Catalogue Specification and the Collection Specification. The service implements the STAC API version v1.0.0-rc.1. The current CreoDIAS STAC API implementation does not support any STAC extensions.

The Collections included and described in the CreoDIAS STAC API:

- LANDSAT-5
- SENTINEL-5P
- SENTINEL-1
- SMOS
- SENTINEL-2
- LANDSAT-8
- ENVISAT
- SENTINEL-3
- TERRAAQUA
- S2GLC
- SENTINEL-1-RTC
- SENTINEL-6
- COP-DEM
- LANDSAT-7

The collections enable searching with simple filtering by:

- `collection_id`
- `items`
- `datetime`

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- `bbox`
- `limit`

In the beginning of year 2023, the new Catalogue API for CREODIAS data catalogue was published. The new Catalogue API relies on a completely new database, which has been adjusted to European Space Agency’s Product Metadata Mapping. Therefore attributes, especially for Sentinel data, have been reorganized and renamed to match the official ESA documentation. These new attribute names (e.g., `productType`) and values (e.g., `GRD`) are present in STAC interfaces.

More details on all changes are available in [R27].

3.6 User-level Metadata Catalogue

The user-level metadata catalogue [R28] is a service that was not originally envisioned as a part of the federation, and – indeed – stands separately alongside the federation, but relies on the experience of the Data federation work package and reuses similar tools.

A result of the user co-design approach employed in C-SCALE, the user-level metadata catalogue addresses the users’ need to keep track of their own data in different scenarios:

- Data cached locally **prior to processing**. This is not strictly necessary but can speed up processing and ease the load on infrastructure in case the same data are accessed many times, e.g., when debugging an automated process or fine-tuning algorithm parameters.
- **Interim** data produced in initial stages of a workflow, and used later on in a following stage.
- De-facto **final** results that should be made discoverable and available to other cooperating users.

The user-level catalogue is implemented as another separate Resto instance, wherein users can request and obtain access rights to publish metadata in their privately managed collections. The user-level catalogue is not included in metadata searches by the EO-MQS for the combined reason that:

1. Metadata are generated by users rather than the actual federation members, who therefore cannot vouch for accuracy or content of the data.
2. More importantly, the locators (URLs) of assets registered in the catalogue do not necessarily have global validity. Users will register interim results using local paths that make sense to their tools, but not generally to a user in a different location.

Hence metadata stored in the user-level catalogue are only useful to users who have registered them, or consumers who are in contact with the originator.

Despite the limitation, the user-level catalogue has been found useful not only by users themselves, but also by compute resource sites, who are not themselves providers of Earth observation data but wanted to cater to their local users and limit data transfers to their site by caching regional data locally for repeated access.

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3.7 Dissemination of Use Case Results

Data federation members distribute primarily large volumes of 3rd party Earth observation products (most notably Sentinel imagery) which serve as an input into analyses performed on C-SCALE infrastructure. However, the results of such analysis may be valid Earth observation products in their own right, and there may be value in making them available to a wider community. Therefore it is possible for data federation providers and use cases to negotiate redistribution of use case results.

In that case, the data provider treats the results as any other type of data they redistribute. They provide storage capacity, make the data accessible, and include them in their metadata catalogue to make them discoverable. The actual technologies or tools to be used in transferring the data from the use case to the provider, and to register metadata in their catalogue, depend on the situation. The same applies to the sharing of responsibilities – whether the originator pushes the data or the provider pulls them, or who is responsible for generating the metadata. But for an outside observer, data generated in that manner are available from the federation (that is: discoverable and accessible) in the same way and under the same conditions as any other type of data on offer.

This approach has been applied in C-SCALE, for instance, to results of the KappaMask use case, which are available from CESNET.

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4 Data Access Implementation

Unlike the discovery part of the Data Federation workload, the central components that enable identity federation services for participating sites are already in place in the wider EOSC ecosystem. Specifically, the Check-in service provided by EGI has been selected for integration. Therefore all effort in this area could be directed at deciding on the common approach and then integrating the individual sites, or – more appropriately – software service stacks they use. The details of their integration are given in the following sections.

4.1 Setting up an Attribute Authority

One of the reasons for identifying users who access the archives is gathering statistical information, which involves specific user attributes. Pre-existing tools such as the Perun identity and access manager [R29] are used to provide users with a single interface where they can register for C-SCALE federation services, both data and cloud compute access, and provide the required details.

For the C-SCALE project, we decided to gather the following attributes across all partners:

- company/organization the user is affiliated with (free text)
- category of user's interest (commercial, education, government, research, other)
- research field (atmosphere, climate, emergency, energy, land, marine, security, other)
- user's function/role (expert, manager, researcher, technician, other)
- user's country
- use cases for which the user registered (e.g., WaterWatch)

The latter (affiliation with use cases) is not actually obtained from the user as an editable attribute, but rather determined by the user's membership in virtual organisations.

4.2 Terrascope Check-in Integration

Terrascope uses Keycloak [R30] to allow user authentication for all web-based services. Keycloak integrates with the FreeIPA [R31] security information solution, storing user credentials in an LDAP repository. The Terrascope platform depends on this custom user repository as various components (Terrascope User Virtual Machines and Hadoop Processing Cluster) require integration with an LDAP or Kerberos service.

Users having an account which is supported by EGI check-in can also use their institutional account to sign-in to web-based Terrascope services (*EduGAIN & social logins* button). Next to EGI check-in, Terrascope also supports the Commercial Operator Identity Hub (COIH) [R32], which is used in the context of ESA NoR (Network of Resources).

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When signing in using an EGI check-in account, a Terrascope user account is created automatically and additional user attributes (e.g., user domain, user function) are collected when the user logs in for the first time. These additional attributes are needed for obligatory reporting towards ESA and EC. The EGI account will be linked to the Terrascope account. In case a Terrascope account already exists for the user's email address, both accounts will be linked.

The additional user attributes may already be available in case a user has joined a C-SCALE VO (Virtual Organization). In that case, these attribute values, which are stored in Perun, will be pre-filled with the values retrieved from the EGI check-in userinfo endpoint.

Figure 4.1: Terrascope interactive sign-in

The Terrascope download service supports two authentication flows:

- **OIDC web-based flow:** a user enters this OpenID Connect flow when using a download link in a web browser. Previously, in case the user does not have a valid Terrascope or EGI session, the user was redirected to the Keycloak sign-in page. In the context of the C-SCALE project, we modified this flow to improve the visibility of the EGI check-in sign-in option as shown in figure 4.2.
- **M2M flow using a bearer token:** a user could already request a Terrascope bearer token and use that to download data. Using an EGI check-in token was not yet supported as the Terrascope download service did not have the possibility to validate EGI check-in tokens. This functionality was added in the context of the C-SCALE project.

The Terrascope download service uses an Apache web server to enable downloads over HTTP. Apache modules `mod_auth_openidc` [R33] and `mod_oauth2` [R34] are added to support the OIDC

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Figure 4.2: Terrascope sign-in with the added EGI Option

and OAuth2 authentication flows. Downloads of EO products are protected by authentication, while downloading previews and metadata is not. While most datasets are public, additional authorization rules can be configured per collection, so only Terrascope users having a specific role are allowed to download the data.

4.3 DHuS-based Check-in Integration

DHuS in its previous versions used to allow users to sign in into the web interface using a login and password, and download images using basic authentication. Users had to register directly into DHuS. In the current version, DHuS is able to offload user registration onto a dedicated Keycloak instance, which is used as a user and password database. Users have to still register directly with this service, the only difference is that the registration is now into Keycloak instead of DHuS (this is based on the SAML authentication protocol). Users can edit their details or reset their passwords, but for the most part DHuS uses this internal Keycloak merely as a password database. In this setup, downloads are protected either with SAML authentication (for web browsers) or with basic authentication (for command-line downloads). Users still have to input their password into the DHuS login page. SAML authentication protocol is only utilized for registration of users and on download URLs, it is not used for signing in, and OIDC is not supported at all. Therefore, it is not possible to let users sign in with existing identities, e.g., via EGI Check-in.

The goal for the C-SCALE project was to allow signing in using EGI Check-in into the web interface and using OIDC bearer tokens from EGI Check-in to authenticate to the download service. Meanwhile, there is also a national user base, which needs to co-exist with C-SCALE users, so actually DHuS is connected to two proxies, EGI Check-in and E-INFRA CZ and serves two user bases (figure 4.4).

To achieve this, we use Apache modules `mod_auth_openidc` and `mod_oauth2` to replace password authentication with standard OIDC authentication flows. For the web interface, we replace the login form with a sign in button, which redirects users to EGI Check-in for authentication.

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Figure 4.3: Terrascope download service

Figure 4.4: Components in the authentication solution for a DHuS-based site at CESNET, including support for a pre-existing national user base E-INFRA.

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Figure 4.5: EGI Check-in authentication tu DHuS through an OIDC bridge.

For the download service (see figure 4.6), Apache verifies the bearer token and forwards the download request with a basic authentication header set.

Figure 4.6: OIDC Authentication against a DHuS-based site – activity diagram

4.4 EODC Check-in Integration

EODC leverages Keycloak to manage authentication and authorization of its users and applications in a secure and efficient manner, much like the Terrascope implementation. Keycloak provides centralized control of access to resources, services, and applications. EODC chose a user directory solution for maximum flexibility and scalable backend support, storing user details in accordance with Lightweight Directory Access Protocol (LDAP) conventions. This protocol establishes basic user attribute requirements, a hierarchical structure, and methods for querying directory contents, making it a reliable source of truth for tools using modern protocols like SAML, OAuth2, and OpenID Connect. Keycloak supports these protocols and offers additional 2-factor authentication options, as well as secure self-registration mechanisms. User details and attributes are exchanged based on the user information

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stored in the LDAP directory. Multiple Keycloak instances run in a highly available and redundant cluster setup for optimal security and reliability.

EODC realizes its data access using an Apache web server together with Keycloak for secure authentication. The Apache module `mod_auth_openidc` is utilized to support the OpenID Connect authentication. EODC as well prioritizes the security of its EO products while making accompanying metadata and preview images easily accessible. Users can access these resources by following a protected link that redirects to the sign-in page. Direct download of a file using an URL already known (typically obtained by a query to the EO-MQS), and providing a valid OIDC token obtained from EGI Check-in, is also supported to facilitate usage by unattended, automated workflows.

Figure 4.7: EODC Login with the EGI option

4.5 CreoDIAS Check-in Integration

Similar to previous solutions, CreoDIAS relies on Keycloak to perform authentication. Authenticating interactively with EGI Check-in is supported (Fig. 4.8), however, CreoDIAS then applies an authorization layer, which is more complicated in comparison to other partners in the federation, and currently requires additional registration steps on first access.

The authentication solution is shared with that used for access to CreoDIAS cloud compute resources, which are also part of C-SCALE's FedEarthData service.

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Sign in to your account

Username or email

Password

[Forgot Password?](#)

Sign In

Or sign in with

EGI Check-in

Figure 4.8: Interactive authentication to CreoDIAS/CloudFerro offering the EGI option

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5 Future Work

5.1 Harmonizing Support of STAC API Extensions

At the moment, different STAC extensions are supported by different implementations of STAC APIs across the federation. Naturally, all sites support STAC Core, but otherwise the coverage is diverse. For instance, currently, the Terrascope STAC API implementation does not support additional STAC extensions. In order to become a valid alternative for the current Terrascope OpenSearch service, the following existing and stable extensions should be considered:

- Projection [R35]
- Electro-Optical [R36]
- Scientific Citation [R37]
- View Geometry [R38]

Although a STAC extension *alternate-assets* exists [R39], which allows to add assets with different access methods (local storage, HTTPS, S3), VITO is considering proposing a new STAC API extension *asset-href-mode* which would allow an end user to specify the data access method so returned assets have the request access method.

5.2 Data Availability Messaging

It is a common problem for many user groups to detect availability of new Earth observation products. In general applications, as well as in all C-SCALE usage scenarios, this is achieved by querying for fresh products in certain intervals. Depending on the given use case's need, this can take place daily or even hourly. No other solution is available to the user community, especially where Sentinel imagery is concerned, however data providers are in a position to set up a messaging system, e.g., a message queue, to advertise incoming products, allowing users to subscribe to notifications and react to new product availability. This would free up load on the querying system, and speed up time-sensitive workflows at the same time.

A similar solution could be used also to advertise products at the other end of their life-cycle, i.e., when products are being taken down for any reason. For instance among ESA Sentinel products, approx. ten thousand products are obsoleted annually for different defects. This is especially difficult to discover, and a notification system capable of advertising discontinued products would generally improve all applications suffering from faulty products being included in, e.g., a time series analysis.

5.3 User-level Metadata Catalogue as a Service

The C-SCALE project has shown that many use cases generate non-trivial amounts of intermediate data products that need to be stored and annotated to make them available for processing in the

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next step of the respective workflow. Thus, it turns out that a common need among many of the user groups consists in setting up a spatio-temporal data catalogue, which helps them keep track of these intermediate products. While not especially complicated, it is a repetitive task and a universal piece in many solutions. Experience from the C-SCALE project shows that users can benefit from such a catalogue service being provided under the „as a service“ paradigm.

The User-level Catalogue differs from C-SCALE’s EO Metadata Query Service (EO-MQS) in that from the point of view of a regular user, it is a read-write catalogue. In other words, the user does not consume catalogue records that have been exposed by a data provider, but rather registers their own records to reuse them later, or even to make them available to other user groups.

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6 Conclusion

The C-SCALE project set out to prototype a distributed archive for Copernicus Earth observation data integrated with processing resources and analytic tools under EOSC. This, on one hand, dictated the technologies to be used in the process, or at least limited the choice of possible approaches. On the other hand, it presented a selection of tools, processes and services already available for reuse and integration.

Given that the Earth observation data platform was to be closely, nay seamlessly integrated with the compute platform, it was only logical to take inspiration from large computing infrastructures available under EOSC, namely the EGI Federated cloud and other EGI computing services, which proved relevant not only to enabling access to processing resources, but also to data.

The C-SCALE Data Federation was able to identify common interfaces and protocols, deliver central services (the EO Metadata Query Service), reuse and integrate with existing infrastructure services (providers' catalogue - GOCDDB, EGI Check-in), and integrate individual providers' service stacks with those central federation services. Through the process of user co-design, additional requirements have been identified (the user-level catalogue) and addressed.

The process to join the federation [R40], and requirements a site must meet to be able to do that, is clearly described and relies on well established services and standards.

C-SCALE results in Earth observation data lookup and access services being available through the EOSC Portal, with providers integrated and poised to supply data readily and seamlessly to users' analytic workflows as per their needs, both for interactive and automated processing. In the context of the original high-level objective of piloting a distributed Copernicus archive, all the required solutions are now in place and what remains is to attract additional providers to fill in the potential gaps, while at the same time working with current providers to expand their coverage where the gaps are most pronounced.

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References

No	Description/Link
R1	EGI Check-in https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/egi-check-in
R2	FedEarthData https://c-scale.eu/services/#FedEarthData
R3	EO-MQS https://c-scale.eu/services/#MQS
R4	D2.1 C-SCALE Copernicus Data Access and Querying Design https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5045317
R5	STAC Specification https://stacspec.org/
R6	GOCDDB https://goc.egi.eu/
R7	stac-fastapi https://github.com/stac-utils/stac-fastapi
R8	FastAPI https://github.com/tiangolo/fastapi
R9	SQLAlchemy https://www.sqlalchemy.org/
R10	EO-MQS Broser https://mqs.eodc.eu/browser
R11	Preview STAC Browser v. 3.0 for EO-MQS https://radiantearth.github.io/stac-browser/#/external/mqs.eodc.eu/stac/v1?.language=en
R12	EO-MQS Help https://mqs.eodc.eu/help
R13	Spring Bot https://spring.io/projects/spring-boot
R14	ElasticSearch https://www.elastic.co/elastic-stack/
R15	Terrascope OpenSearch STAC Adapter repository https://github.com/VIT0belgium/opensearch-stac-adapter
R16	Terrascope OpenSearch STAC Adapter API documentation https://services.terrascope.be/stac/docs
R17	DHuS https://sentineldatahub.github.io/DataHubSystem/about.html
R18	Copernicus Open Access Hub https://scihub.copernicus.eu/
R19	DHuS OpenSearch API Documentation https://scihub.copernicus.eu/userguide/OpenSearchAPI
R20	DHuS OData API Documentation https://scihub.copernicus.eu/userguide/ODataAPI
R21	Resto https://github.com/jjrom/resto
R22	STAC Tools https://github.com/stactools-packages

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R23	DHuS Tools https://github.com/CESNET/DHuSTools
R24	CESNET STAC endpoint https://stac.cesnet.cz/
R25	GRNET STAC endpoint https://resto.einfra.grnet.gr/
R26	CreoDIAS STAC API https://datahub.creodias.eu/stac/
R27	CreoDIAS Catalogue Mapping https://creodias.eu/documents/portlet_file_entry/20182/Catalogue_mapping_rev2.xls/02b49fcb-2ee5-4e84-ace3-5be76e8ceeb6?download=true
R28	User-level Metadata Catalogue https://resto.c-scale.zcu.cz/
R29	Perun https://perun-aai.org/
R30	Keycloak https://www.keycloak.org/
R31	FreeIPA https://www.freeipa.org
R32	Commercial Operator Identity Hub (COIH) https://coih.org/
R33	Module mod_auth_openidc for the Apache Web Server https://github.com/zmartzone/mod_auth_openidc
R34	Module mod_oauth2 for the Apache Web Server https://github.com/zmartzone/mod_oauth2
R35	Projection Extension Specification https://github.com/stac-extensions/projection
R36	Electro-Optical Extension Specification https://github.com/stac-extensions/eo
R37	Scientific Citation Extension Specification https://github.com/stac-extensions/scientific
R38	View Geometry Extension Specification https://github.com/stac-extensions/view
R39	Alternate Assets Extension Specification https://github.com/stac-extensions/alternate-assets
R40	Data Federation Providers' Guide https://wiki.c-scale.eu/C-SCALE/c-scale-providers

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Appendix 1 – How FAIR is C-SCALE Data?

This questionnaire is based on work by Jones, Sarah, & Grootveld, Marjan. (2017). *How FAIR are your data?* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5111307>. It reflects the current status of the data federation at the time of releasing this Report. Some aspects may improve even by the end of the C-SCALE project.

A note to the reader: The C-SCALE Data federation does not produce its own data, and relies on Copernicus and other spatio-temporal data providers in that department. That is why some of the points in this questionnaire are answered conditionally, with reference to common practice seen at the biggest providers. That said, it is the mission of C-SCALE to make data more findable and accessible, so that answering some of these questions is highly relevant. The reader is duly reminded in our comments on questions that are outside our control.

Findable

It should be possible for others to discover your data. Rich metadata should be available online in a searchable resource, and the data should be assigned a persistent identifier.

A persistent identifier is assigned to your data

Comment: A vast majority of data available through the C-SCALE Data Federation originate from the Sentinel programme, which uses a fixed, unique identifier (ID) and a human readable Title to refer to any of its products. Given the redundant nature of storage providers within the Sentinel collaborative ground segment,¹ or – for that matter – within the C-SCALE federation, a single product (determined by its ID or Title) can be obtainable from multiple sources and the address of the potential provider is not a part of the identifier. Searching for that identifier through a search interface – be it it C-SCALE EO-MQS or any Copernicus dissemination node, however, always leads to the same piece of data, albeit from a different storage site. Moreover, an MD5 checksum is provided among Sentinel metadata, which makes it possible to affirm that the same original data file is indeed being accessed, regardless of the location from where it is being obtained.

There are rich metadata, describing your data

Comment: Metadata follow the STAC standard² and include rich characteristics of each given product in terms of its origins, parameters, and contents.

¹<https://sentinels.copernicus.eu/web/sentinel/missions/collaborative>

²<https://stacspec.org/>

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The metadata are online in a searchable resource e.g. a catalogue or data repository

Comment: The metadata are available through STAC-API,³ STAC Browser,⁴ and through STAC /search⁵ endpoints, which are all exposed by the EO-MQS.

The metadata record specifies the persistent identifier

Comment: This is partly true. The metadata record specifies only the Title, which is enough to identify the product through searching the catalogue, but not to reference it directly.

Accessible

It should be possible for humans and machines to gain access to your data, under specific conditions or restrictions where appropriate. FAIR does not mean that data need to be open! There should be metadata, even if the data aren't accessible.

Following the persistent ID will take you to the data or associated metadata

Comment: A vast majority of data available through the C-SCALE Data Federation originate from the Sentinel programme, wherewith it is necessary to look up the persistent ID in EO-MQS (or a different catalogue outside C-SCALE) to obtain download links for the data. It is not a locator by itself. A metadata search returns relevant locators that can be followed to download the data from the FedEarthData service.

Furthermore, it is one of the primary characteristics of the C-SCALE Data federation that it reveals the location of multiple copies of the same data file, if available from multiple providers in the federation. It is left to the user do choose among them, based on any preference they may have. Using a definite URL as an identifier would defy that trait of the federation.

The protocol by which data can be retrieved follows recognised standards e.g. http

Comment: The protocol is HTTPS.

The access procedure includes authentication and authorisation steps, if necessary

Comment: Authentication is performed when accessing data from most providers of the FedEarth-Data service. All these sites support OIDC-based single sign-on authentication through EGI Check-in. Sites are also free to offer the data openly, without authentication, if their policies allow that.

³<https://mqs.eodc.eu/stac/v1/>

⁴<https://mqs.eodc.eu/browser>

⁵<https://mqs.eodc.eu/stac/v1/search>

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Metadata are accessible, wherever possible, even if the data aren't

Comment: Metadata provided by partners and aggregated by the EO-MQS are openly accessible, authentication is only required on actual access when contacting the FedEarthData service.

Interoperable

Data and metadata should conform to recognised formats and standards to allow them to be combined and exchanged.

Data is provided in commonly understood and preferably open formats

Comment: A vast majority of data available through the C-SCALE Data Federation originate from the Sentinel programme, and follow SAFE (Standard Archive Format for Europe).⁶

The metadata provided follows relevant standards

Comment: Metadata follow the STAC (Spatio-Temporal Assets Catalogue) format.

Controlled vocabularies, keywords, thesauri or ontologies are used where possible

Comment: Terminology follows the STAC (Spatio-Temporal Assets Catalogue) standard, namely the Core specification.

Qualified references and links are provided to other related data

Comment: Related links are provided pursuant to the STAC (Spatio-Temporal Assets Catalogue) specification.

Reusable

Lots of documentation is needed to support data interpretation and reuse. The data should conform to community norms and be clearly licensed so others know what kinds of reuse are permitted.

The data are accurate and well described with many relevant attributes

Comment: A vast majority of data available through the C-SCALE Data Federation originate from the Sentinel programme, which is amply documented and supported by numerous tools.

⁶<https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/activities/safe-the-standard-archive-format-for-europe>

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The data have a clear and accessible data usage license

Comment: A vast majority of data available through the C-SCALE Data Federation originate from the Sentinel programme and are released under the Creative Commons CC BY-SA 3.0 IGO license.⁷ This is specified in documentation but not included with actual data.

It is clear how, why and by whom the data have been created and processed

Comment: A vast majority of data available through the C-SCALE Data Federation originate from the Sentinel programme, and their origin and level of processing are documented with metadata available both in catalogues and included with the actual data. On top of that there is a data provenance service by ESA, which provides further detail on processing and distribution history for each data point.

The data and metadata meet relevant domain standards

Comment: Indeed the data and metadata not only follow but even define the relevant domain standard.

⁷<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/igo/>

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